

Paper 8

**A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SOCIAL MATURITY
OF B.ED. TRAINEES**

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ABSTRACT

The present study titled ‘A study on Emotional Intelligence and Social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.’ The main aim of the study was to find out the level of Emotional Intelligence and Social maturity of B.Ed. trainees as well as to find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Social maturity. The sample of the study was 125 student teachers by simple random sampling method from Srinivas university college of education Mangalore. A standardized tool a) Social maturity scale developed by Dr. Nalini Rao and b) Sevenfold Emotional Intelligence scale developed by Dr. Vinit kher, M S Puja Ahuja & M S Sarbjit Kaur were used. The statistical techniques used in the study were mean, SD and ‘t’ test further Karl Pearson’s product moment correlation. Major findings of the study revealed that both urban and rural, science and arts students possess equal level of Emotional Intelligence and Social maturity. Further, the analysis revealed that 74% student teachers possess moderate level of Emotional Intelligence and 70% student teachers possess moderate level of Social maturity. It is also found that there is no correlation between Social maturity and Emotional Intelligence. Some strategies to strengthen the Social maturity and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. trainees are suggested in the study.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Social maturity, B.Ed. trainees, relationship.

1.0.0 Introduction

Education means all round drawing out of the best in child and man- body, mind and spirit according to Gandhiji. Main aim of education is overall development of personality, that means education must make a man physically, socially, morally, intellectually mature. In the process of education teacher has to play different roles like guide, philosopher, trainer, stage setter, councilor etc. Teacher training institutions have vital roles in ensuring adequate development of knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for teaching.

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Man is a social animal. Society plays a significant role in man's life. To lead peaceful and harmonious life he must follow societal norms and rules. The capability to function in a responsible manner by understanding society's norms and rules as well as effectively using this knowledge is called social maturity. It is the possession of right attitude by an individual which are very essential for the effective functioning of the society (Pushpa 2015)

Social maturity means knowing what to do and striving for it by following acceptable social behavior. To be socially mature one should follow those people who are socially mature.

According to Hurlock (1950) social development means attaining maturity in social relations. It means the process of learning to conform to group standards, morals and traditions and becoming imbued with a sense of oneness, inter-communications and co-operation". Socially matured person contribute for social unity, take right decisions work selflessly for the betterment of the society. Social maturity produces a climate of trust, harmony active co-operation and peaceful co-existence. According to Goleman emotional intelligence as the capacity to reason with emotion in four areas: to perceive emotion, to integrate in thoughts, to understand and to manage it. Bar-on (1997) said that emotional intelligence reflects once ability to deal with daily environment challenges and helps predict one's success in life including professional and personal pursuits. According to Salovey (1990) emotional intelligence consists of five characteristics they are self-awareness or knowing one's own emotions, the ability to manage one's emotions and impulses, self-motivation, ability to sense how others are feeling and social skills or the ability to handle the emotions of other people. According to Mayer and Cobb (2000) emotional intelligence is the ability to process emotional information, and it includes perception, assimilation, understanding and management of emotions. Emotional intelligent is a different way of being smart. It helps us to know what are our feelings and helps us to take good decisions in our life and manage stressful situation in an effective manner. Emotional intelligent person can be able to control his impulses. Persons with higher emotional intelligence are found to be more social.

Education is not a static, but a dynamic process. There are lots of changes have been made in the process of education. What worked well in the past may not be so effective in the present. Changes in education takes place according to the changes in the society and it is very essential to maintain total quality in education. The role of teacher in education is very important and crucial. To cope with the changes teachers also must possess essential qualities. Among these qualities emotional intelligence and social maturity is equally important.

1.1.0 Need of the study

There are different factors that play a very important role in maintaining total quality in education. For this the teachers should have certain essential characteristics such as intelligent, empathetic, aware of personal and social responsibility, fair and impartial, friendly democratic, dynamic etc. As per the above characteristics it is important that the student teachers also should have emotional intelligence and social maturity. Hence the researcher has chosen this area for the present study. The research outlined in this study attempted to identify and understand the emotional intelligence and social maturity levels of student teachers. So, in the light of all these, the researchers felt the need of assessing social maturity and emotional intelligence of student teachers. The need analyzed above raises the following questions;

1. To what extent student teachers possess social maturity?
2. To what extent student teachers possess emotional intelligence?
3. Is there any relationship between emotional intelligence and social maturity?

1.2.0 Statement of the problem

Adolescence is the transitional stage of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. This is the period of establishment of personal values, self-sufficiency and they wanted to play an independent role in the society. To manage these adolescences there is a need of an effective teacher. So, it is important to develop such potential teachers who are socially matured and emotionally intelligent. With this intension the researcher made an attempt to know about the level of social maturity and emotional intelligence and to measure correlation between Emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees. The study entitled as ‘A study on emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.’

1.3.1 Objectives of the study:

- 1) To find out the level of social maturity and emotional intelligence of student teachers
- 2) To study whether there is any significant difference between arts and science student teachers in social maturity and emotional intelligence
- 3) To study whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in social maturity and emotional intelligence.
- 4) To study whether there exists any significant relationship between social maturity and emotional intelligence of student teachers.

1.3.2 Hypothesis of the study

1. There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in social maturity and emotional intelligence.
2. There is no significant difference between arts and science student teacher's in social maturity and emotional intelligence
3. There is no significant relationship between social maturity and emotional intelligence of student teachers

1.3.3 Method of the study

The study is descriptive in nature and survey method was used. 125 B.Ed. trainees from Srinivas College of education Mangalore were selected randomly as the sample of the study. For collection of required data the investigator prepared google form and sent the tool through WhatsApp group to student teachers and asked them to fill the form. The student teachers were asked to respond to all the questions. They were asked to select according to their choice on the alternatives provided.

1.3.4 Sample

A sample is a small portion of population selected for observation and analysis. The sample for the present study comprised 125 student teachers randomly selected from Srinivas University.

1.3.5 Tools used for data collection

To measure the selected variables following standardized tools were used.

- a) Social maturity scale developed by Dr. Nalini Rao's and
- b) Sevenfold emotional intelligence scale developed by Dr. Vinit kher, M S Puja Ahuja & M S Sarbjit Kaur

1.4.0 Statistical techniques used

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, data have been analyzed and interpreted by giving statistical treatment. The tabulation and analysis of data were done by using appropriate statistical technique such as mean, Standard Deviation and 't' test and further Karl Pearson's product moment correlation.

1.5.0 Analysis and interpretation of data

The presentation of the results and their interpretation has been done objective wise.

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1.5.1 Analysis of objective One

The first objective of the study was to find out the levels of emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.

The following table shows the frequencies of then scores on emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.

Table1.1: showing the frequencies of then scores on emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.

Variable	High		Moderate		Low	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Emotional Intelligence	19	15%	92	74%	14	11%
Social maturity	17	14%	88	70%	20	16%

Table 1.1 reveals that 15% of B.Ed. trainee’s exhibit high level, 74% of B.Ed. trainees exhibit moderate and 11% of B.Ed. trainees exhibited low level of emotional maturity.

In relation to social maturity 14% of B.Ed. trainees exposed high level, 70% have exposed moderate level and 16% of B.Ed. trainees exposed low level of social maturity.

Thus, it is concluded that majority of B.Ed. trainees possess moderate level of emotional intelligence and social maturity.

1.5.2 Analysis of objective Two

The second objective of the study was to find out whether there is any significant difference between Urban and Rural B.Ed., trainees in social maturity and emotional intelligence. The data was analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 1.2

Table 1.2: Summary of N, Mean, SD, t-value of the scores of Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity of with respect to locality

Variables	group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Result
Emotional Intelligence	Urban	60	196.08	11.40	1.50	Not significant at 0.01 level
	Rural	65	192.74	13.61		
Social Maturity	Urban	63	291.83	24.98	1.87	Not significant at 0.01 level
	Rural	62	283.61	24.25		

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From the table 1.2 it is revealed that the calculated ‘t’ value of emotional intelligence is 1.50, which is less than the table value (2.65) at 0.01 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, and concluded that there is no significant difference between rural and urban B.Ed. trainees in emotional intelligence.

The above table indicates that the obtained ‘t’ value of social maturity is 1.87, which is less than the table value (2.65) at 0.01 level. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, and concluded that there is no significant difference between rural and urban B.Ed. trainees in social maturity.

Thus, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between urban B.Ed. trainees and rural B.Ed. trainees in emotional intelligence and social maturity. It means that both urban and rural B.Ed. trainees possess more or less similar level of emotional intelligence and social maturity.

1.5.3 Analysis of objective Three

The third objective of the study was to find out whether there is any significant difference between arts and science B.Ed. trainees in social maturity and emotional intelligence. The data was analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 1.3

Table 1.3: Summary of N, Mean, SD, t-value of the scores of Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity with respect to their stream of their subjects

Variables	group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Result
Emotional Intelligence	Science	60	194.58	12.74	0.39	Not significant at 0.01 level
	Arts	65	195.45	12.65		
Social Maturity	Science	62	292.23	24.58	1.63	Not significant at 0.01 level
	Arts	63	285.24	23.46		

From the table 1.3, it is revealed that the calculated ‘t’ value of emotional intelligence is 0.39, which is less than the table value (2.65) at 0.01 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, and concluded that there is no significant difference between science and rural B.Ed. trainees in emotional intelligence.

The above table indicates that the obtained ‘t’ value of social maturity is 1.63, which is less than the table value (2.65) at 0.01 level. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, and concluded that there is no significant difference between science and arts B.Ed. trainees in social maturity.

Thus, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between science B.Ed. trainees and arts

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B.Ed. trainees in emotional intelligence and social maturity. It means that both science and arts B.Ed. trainees possess more or less similar level of emotional intelligence and social maturity.

1.5.4 Analysis of objective four

The fourth objective of the study was to find out the relationship between social maturity and emotional intelligence of B.Ed. trainees. The data was analyzed and interpreted using Product-moment correlation ‘r’ and null hypothesis was formulated in relation to this objective.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees.

The value of ‘r’ is -0.018 for the level of significance at 0.01 with df =123. The result is given in the table 1.4

Table 1.4: showing the Mean, S.D, ‘r’ value and the level of significance

Variables	N	Mean	SD	‘r’ value	Result
Emotional Intelligence	125	193.81	12.72	-0.01802	Not significant at 0.01 level
Social Maturity	125	288.70	24.24		

Table 1.4 from the above table 1.4, it is clear that ‘r’ value between emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees is found to be **-0.01802** which is not significant at 0.01 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and social maturity of B.Ed. trainees. The findings revealed that Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity are independent factors. It means that person’s social maturity does not have any impact on Emotional Intelligence and vice versa.

1.6.0 Major findings of the study

1. It is found that majority of the B.Ed. trainees possess moderate level of Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity.
2. It is found that there is no significant difference between Urban and Rural B.Ed. trainees in relation to Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity
3. that there is no significance difference between Science and Arts student teachers in relation to Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity
4. Research concludes there is no significance relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity

1.7.0. Educational implications of the study

1. As the result revealed that majority of the student teachers possess moderate and low level of Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity. Hence teacher education centers should organize skill based programs to improve Emotional Intelligence and Social Maturity of B.Ed. trainees, like seminars, special lectures, life skills and social skills training programs etc.
2. Teacher educators should adopt constructivist teaching- learning strategies to make the individuals aware of themselves and others.
3. Teacher educators are the role models to student teachers. So, they should possess high level of emotional intelligence and social maturity.
4. Special guidance would be needed for B.Ed. trainees to develop their emotional intelligence and social maturity.
5. Various social and community based programs should be organized and student teachers should be inspired to participate in such programs.
6. The teacher educators should adopt issue based teaching learning strategies taking real life situations to make the individuals aware of themselves and others.
7. It is essential to reform the curriculum with ample opportunities for practical knowledge.
8. Emotionally mature people self-aware and intuitive. Hence more and more self-awareness programs can be organized in college level.

1.8.0 Delimitations of the study

- 1) The study was confined to student teachers of Srinivas University college of education.
- 2) The sample was restricted to the student teachers pursuing B.Ed. course.
- 3) The sample size was restricted to 125 student teachers only
- 4) The study is limited to collect information about independent variables like location of residence and stream of study
- 5) The study is limited to only studying two dependent variables emotional intelligence and social maturity.

1.9.0 Suggestions for the further research

- a) A study on social maturity and emotional intelligence can be done on different professional students (nursing, agricultural, engineering, medical students).
- b) A study on social maturity and emotional intelligence of juvenile children with that of normal school students can be done.

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- c) Role of family, Effect of yoga and meditation in development of emotional intelligence and social maturity can be done.
- d) A study on these variables of tribes, slum students can be done.

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